

FAIR Guideline for ARDC Co-investment Project Data Outputs

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REVIEW DATE	April 2027
TYPE	Guideline
OWNER	Manager, Skilled Workforce Development, ARDC Research Data Specialist (FAIR), ARDC
APPROVED BY	Director of Outreach
CATEGORY	Projects
VERSION NUMBER	1.6.1
AUDIENCE	External
CONTENT ENQUIRIES	contact@ardc.edu.au
RELATED DOCUMENTS	FAIR Policy: ARDC or ARDC Co-Invested Materials Guideline for Partners: Exceptions on openness of Partnership Materials
DEFINITIONS	FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP): A list of declared technology choices intended to implement each of the FAIR Principles for ARDC co-investment project data outputs

<p>PURPOSE</p>	<p>Provide an approach for ARDC co-investment projects to progress their application of the FAIR principles to data and data outputs.</p>
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Context

The ARDC is a National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) facility, and it is the policy of the Commonwealth NCRIS program that “data generated, created, captured or stored by NCRIS funded projects will be made available to the wider research community based on the F.A.I.R. principles” ([National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy 2023 Guidelines](#)).

The ARDC encourages the adoption of the [FAIR Principles](#) as a valuable way of making research outputs more reusable, both for humans and machines. This guideline applies specifically to data and data outputs from ARDC co-investment projects, however all co-investment projects are expected to report on their efforts to ensure their project outputs align with the FAIR principles, as outlined in the [FAIR Policy: ARDC or ARDC Co-Invested Materials](#).

Approach

ARDC staff will support co-investment projects to apply the FAIR Principles to the project data outputs across the project lifecycle. To that end, FAIR will be considered in the preparation of the project plan and relevant milestones will be tracked through progress and final reports.

Project Plans should include a FAIR initiation activity as part of an early Work Package. The FAIR initiation activity will include a consultation about FAIR with the project team and facilitated by ARDC Thematic RDC Skills Development Leads. This will assist ARDC to establish a project’s relative FAIR maturity and requirements for ARDC support, and to recommend actions and objectives for demonstrating progress in relation to FAIR.

The support provided by ARDC staff may include a range of activities and tools including, but not limited to:

- Consultation with project leads on FAIR implementation specific to the project’s context
- FAIR workshops with project teams
- Guidance and advice on completing a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) for the project data outputs using the GO FAIR [FIP Mini-Questionnaire](#) and/or [FIP Wizard](#) (which stores the FIP for future edits and publication).